

E6.1 Validation methodology design and plan v1.0

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**Programa de Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión –
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4 List of Acronyms

CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
DevOps	Development and Operations
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load
FEAST	Feature Store
FPS	Frame Per Second
Holo	Holographic
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
Kubectl	Kubernetes Control
LCM	Life-cycle Management
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLaaS	ML as a Service
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
PCI	Peripheral Component Interconnect
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
XAI	eXplainable AI

5 Executive Summary

Deliverable E6.1 outlines the validation plan in the framework of task A6.1, focusing on the deployment steps of key project components, along with a detailed timeline. It includes setting up the testbed with "Higher End" and "Edge" servers, deploying the i2CAT Holoportation Stack, OPTARE distributed monitoring platform, I2CAT MLOps Kubeflow pipeline, and OpenNebula orchestrator¹. The designed architecture integrates Kubernetes clusters and namespaces for efficient application deployment, with the Edge cluster using OpenNebula to manage containerized workloads. The cloud cluster features namespaces for MLOps and telemetry to enhance control and scalability, with inter-namespace communication facilitated through Kubernetes APIs. The Holoportation setup includes Holo Comm Server installation on the K8s Edge server, Holo Client connections, and Holo Orchestrator for session management. Prometheus and OPTARE telemetry platforms manage KPIs and metrics such as frame-per-second (FPS), delay and inbound/outbound bandwidths, before storing them in InfluxDB and managing features via FEAST. The i2CAT MLOps provides AI services to the OpenNebula Edge orchestrator and triggers retraining based on new data. The orchestrator deployment includes front-end, virtualization hosts, networking, and multi-tenancy configuration.

¹ Thanks to OPTARE and OpenNebula for the provided descriptions of their respective deployment plans.

6 Introduction

Holoportation, an advanced telepresence technology enabling real-time 3D interaction, exemplifies the transformative potential of 6G networks with its stringent demands for ultra-low latency, high bandwidth, and reliable connectivity. Deliverable E6.1 outlines the validation methodology and deployment plan for key components essential for such use-case, including the i2CAT Holoportation Stack, OPTARE distributed monitoring platform, I2CAT MLOps Kubeflow pipeline, and OpenNebula orchestrator. The i2CAT Holoportation Stack is central to providing immersive telepresence experiences, crucial for applications in remote collaboration, healthcare, and education within 6G environments. The OPTARE distributed monitoring platform ensures real-time performance tracking and reliability, vital for maintaining the high standards expected of 6G networks. The I2CAT MLOps Kubeflow pipeline automates machine learning workflows, providing predictive maintenance and optimization of network resources, which are essential for the dynamic and adaptive nature of 6G. The OpenNebula orchestrator manages virtualized resources and orchestrates containerized workloads at edge, facilitating the dynamic scaling and efficient resource utilization needed to handle the variable demands of 6G applications. Utilizing a testbed with "Higher End" and "Edge" servers, the architecture integrates Kubernetes clusters and namespaces for scalable and efficient application deployment. Segmented namespaces in the cloud environment enhance control, resource allocation, and fault isolation, allowing for independent scaling and management of resources. Inter-namespace communication facilitated through Kubernetes APIs ensures secure and efficient data exchange and service interaction, which is essential for the seamless operation of complex 6G network functions.

7 Testbed & Infrastructure Setup

The testbed consists of two servers, namely "Higher End" and "Edge," both hosting Kubernetes clusters. They present the key features shown in Table 1:

Table 1 Testbed components

Server	Key Features	K8s Namespace	Functionality
Higher End Server (Cloud)	<p>1. Dual AMD EPYC™ 7003/7002 Series Processors (The latest AMD EPYC™ 7003 Series Processor with AMD 3D V-Cache™ Technology requires BIOS version 2.3 or newer)</p> <p>2. 8TB Registered ECC DDR4 3200MHz SDRAM in 32 DIMMs</p> <p>3. Expansion slots: 2 PCI-E 4.0 x16 (FH, 10.5" L) slots, 1 PCI-E 4.0 x16 (FH, 9.5" L) slot, 1 PCI-E 4.0 x16 (LP) slot, 1 PCI-E 4.0 x8 (FH, 9.5" L, in x16) slot, 1 PCI-E 4.0 x8 (internal proprietary LP in x16) slot.</p> <p>4. Integrated IPMI 2.0 + KVM with dedicated LAN</p> <p>• Software Out of Band License key (SFT-OOB-LIC) included for OOB BIOS management</p> <p>5. Dual 10GBase-T LAN ports via Intel® X710-AT2</p> <p>6. 12 hot-swap 3.5" Drive Bays: 12 SATA3 by default or 8 SATA3 + 4 NVMe via optional tray or 12 SAS3 via optional SAS kit</p> <p>7. 1600W Redundant Power Supplies Titanium Level (96%+) (Full redundancy based on configuration and application load)</p>	<p>-MLOps Namespace: Dedicated namespace for machine learning operations, including model training, inference, and resource allocation.</p> <p>-Telemetry Namespace: Namespace for OPTARE telemetry data aggregation and analysis.</p>	<p>-Aggregates telemetry data from the Edge server via the OPTARE platform.</p> <p>-Hosts the i2CAT MLOps pipeline for training and deploying machine learning models.</p>
Edge Server	<p>1. Single AMD EPYC™ 7002/7003 Series Processor (The latest AMD EPYC™ 7003 Series Processor with AMD 3D V-Cache™ Technology requires BIOS version 2.3 or newer)</p> <p>2. 16 DIMMs; up to 4TB 3DS ECC DDR4-3200MHz RDIMM/LRDIMM</p> <p>3. Expansion slots: 2 PCI-E 4.0 x16 (FHHL) slots, 2 AIOM slots for flexible networking (One x8 AIOM slot and one x16 AIOM slot)</p> <p>4. Integrated IPMI 2.0 + KVM with dedicated LAN</p> <p>• Software Out of Band License key (SFT-OOB-LIC) included for OOB BIOS management</p> <p>5. 10 Hot-swap 2.5" SATA3 drive bays, optional 10x SAS3/NVMe support via additional SAS/NVMe kit</p> <p>M.2 Interface: 2 PCI-E 4.0 x4 M.2 Form Factor: 2242, 2260, 2280, 22110 M.2 Key: M-Key</p> <p>6. 2 USB 3.0 ports (rear), 1 VGA, 1 COM, ASPEED AST2600 BMC graphics</p> <p>7. Tool-less Drive Trays and Tool-less Brackets</p>	<p>Default namespace, including OpenNebula orchestrator and holoportation application</p>	<p>-Executes the holoportation application stack</p> <p>-Dynamically scales the holoportation application stack based on recommendations from the resource allocation model.</p> <p>-Sends telemetry data to the Higher End server for aggregation and analysis.</p>

E6.1 Validation methodology design and plan

	8.860W Redundant Platinum Level Power Supplies <i>(Full redundancy based on configuration and application load)</i>		
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By utilizing this testbed configuration, 6GENABLERS-AI can validate and test the described architecture in a controlled environment. The distributed nature of the infrastructure allows for geographic distribution of workloads related to artificial intelligence, ensuring efficient resource utilization and scalability across cloud and edge environments.

8 Validation Architecture and Deployment

Figure 1 Validation architecture

In the designed architecture illustrated in Figure 1, integrating Kubernetes clusters and namespaces is crucial for efficient and scalable application and service deployment. Central to this architecture is the robust management of resources and isolation of functionalities to ensure seamless operation. The Edge cluster, responsible for executing the holoportation application stack and core network functions, uses OpenNebula to orchestrate containerized workloads across distributed nodes, enabling dynamic scaling and load balancing to handle variable demand and ensure optimal performance.

The cloud environment is segmented into two distinct namespaces: one for MLOps pipeline operations and the other for telemetry and InfluxDB data aggregation. This separation enhances organizational control and resource allocation, simplifying management and ensuring scalability and fault isolation. The isolated MLOps pipeline namespace allows resources to be allocated and scaled independently based on machine learning workflow requirements, without affecting the performance of other components.

Inter-namespace communication is facilitated through Kubernetes APIs and service discovery mechanisms, allowing the MLOps pipeline namespace to use Kubernetes Services to exchange data and information with the telemetry namespace. Additionally, Kubernetes network policies control traffic flow between namespaces, ensuring secure and efficient communication while maintaining isolation. The dedicated namespace for

MLOps operations offers i) streamlined deployment and management with a focused environment for model training, testing, and inference, and ii) scalability.

The trained resource allocation model within the MLOps namespace enhances Edge functionality by guiding resource distribution and optimization. The Edge cluster leverages this model to dynamically scale the holoportation application stack based on real-time demand and performance metrics. Integrating insights from MLOps operations enables the Edge cluster to adapt to changing conditions, ensuring efficient resource utilization while maintaining high-quality service delivery.

8.1 Holoportation Stack deployment plan

Figure 2 Holoportation application setup

Figure 2 illustrates the holoportation application setup architecture. The Comm Server will be installed on the K8s Edge server, after which Holo Clients (User Equipment) will connect to the testbed. The necessary hardware for Holo Clients will be provided, requiring only Ethernet connectivity to a port, switch, or Customer Premises Equipment (CPE). Bandwidth requirements per uplink/downlink stream are around 20 Mbps.

The Holo Orchestrator, responsible for session management and control information, will be supplied as a Docker image for Edge server deployment. Data Plane traffic will be secured via TCP WebSockets.

For KPIs and metrics, Prometheus will be provided with the following capabilities:

Metric	Description	Importance
Real-time Client Metrics		
Delays	Time taken for data to travel from the source to the client and back	Ensures low latency for seamless interaction and avoids motion sickness

Bandwidth	Amount of data transmitted per second to the client	Maintains smooth delivery of high-quality, data-intensive XR content
Frames per Second (fps)	Number of frames displayed per second	Provides smooth motion and immersive experience; higher fps results in less choppy visuals
Real-time Server Metrics		
Inbound Bandwidth	Amount of data received by the server per second	Ensures the server can handle incoming data from multiple clients without becoming overwhelmed
Outbound Bandwidth	Amount of data sent from the server to the clients per second	Ensures efficient delivery of high-quality XR content to all connected clients

8.2 OPTARE distributed monitoring platform deployment plan

OPTARE telemetry platform collects the holoportation stack metrics through an exporter. These raw data is then stored in InfluxDB and aggregated using Feature Store (FEAST). It facilitates efficient management of data features, crucial for both offline training and online inference. This integration ensures consistency in model behaviour across different operational stages and enhances data visibility and access during critical decision-making processes.

Figure 3 Planned deployment of the distributed telemetry system

The components of this distributed telemetry system are:

- **Edge Components**
 - **Cert Manager:** Responsible for managing security certificates in the edge environment.
 - **Otel Operator:** Operates and manages the collection of telemetry data using the OpenTelemetry SDK Client.
 - **K8s Cluster Metrics Collector:** Collects CPU, memory, and network metrics from the Kubernetes cluster at the edge.
 - **App Metrics Collector:** Collects custom metrics from the Holotransportation applications at the edge.

- **Cloud Components**
 - **Cert Manager:** Similar to the edge component, it manages security certificates in the cloud environment.
 - **Otel Operator:** Operates and manages the collection of telemetry data in the cloud.
 - **Gateway Metrics Collector:** Collects metrics through a gateway.
 - **Observability backend (influxDB2 and Grafana):** Platform for storing and visualizing the collected metrics.
 - **ETL system (airflow):** Data extraction, transformation, and loading system.
 - **Data warehouse (PostgreSQL):** Data warehouse using PostgreSQL.
 - **Feature store (FEAST):** Feature store used to manage and store feature data, exposing a REST API for online and offline data services using GET methods.

The interaction of these components is as follows:

- **Edge k8s cluster:** This cluster contains several pods and services managed by **OPENB**. Holotransportation applications run in containers, and telemetry data is collected by **OTel** through *the OpenTelemetry SDK Client*.
- **Data Transmission to the Cloud:** Telemetry data is sent from the edge cluster to the cloud through specified external IP addresses (<CLOUD-EXTERNAL-IP-O.DOMAIN>:4318).
- **Cloud k8s cluster:** In the cloud, telemetry data is managed by various components:
 - **otel-gateway:** Receives the data and passes it through a load balancer to the observability components (OTel, influxDB2).
 - **influxDB2 and grafana:** Store and visualize the data for analysis.

- **ETL (airflow):** Processes the data and stores it in the **Data warehouse (PostgreSQL)**.
- **Feature store (FEAST):** Manages feature data, distributing between online and offline data through load balancers and cluster IPs, exposing a REST API for providing online and offline data services using GET methods.
- **FEAST Services:**
 - **External Consumption:** <CLOUD-EXTERNAL-IP-O.DOMAIN>:30100 is used for consuming the FEAST service from outside the cluster.
 - **Internal Consumption:** feast.svc.cluster.local:30101 is used for consuming the FEAST service from within the cluster.

8.3 I2CAT distributed MLOps Kubeflow pipeline deployment plan

Figure 4 MLOps Kubeflow-containerized implementation

The i2CAT MLOps provides predictive AI services to the OpenNebula Edge orchestrator, to guide its OneFlow scaling policies. The MLOps pipeline also triggers retraining upon the reception of new data from OPTARE’s feature store, FEAST, to meet the target model's confidence. As detailed in deliverable E3.6.2, the pipeline consists of i) Statistical Data Aggregation, ii) Model Training, Confidence Evaluation and Saving and iii) Model Serving and Deployment.

To deploy this Kubeflow-based pipeline, the following steps are planned:

- **Prerequisites**
 - **Kubect!**: Install and configure kubectl to interact with the Kubernetes cluster.
 - **Namespaces:** Ensure monitoring namespace for FEAST telemetry are already created and configured.
- **Steps**
 - **Create Namespace for Kubeflow:** Creates the mlops namespace where Kubeflow components will be deployed.

```
kubectl create namespace mlops
```

- **Install Kubeflow:**

- **Download Kubeflow Manifests:**

```
git clone https://github.com/kubeflow/manifests.git
cd manifests
```

- **Deploy Kubeflow:** Downloads and applies the Kubeflow manifests to deploy Kubeflow in the mlops namespace.

```
kustomize build example | kubectl apply -f - -n mlops
```

- **Verify Kubeflow Installation:** Checks the status of the deployed pods in the mlops namespace to ensure they are running correctly.

```
kubectl get pods -n mlops
```

- **Access Kubeflow Dashboard:**

- **Set Up Port Forwarding:** Forwards the port to access the Kubeflow dashboard from a local machine.

```
kubectl port-forward svc/istio-ingressgateway -n istio-system
8080:80
```

- **Navigate to the Dashboard:** Opens the Kubeflow dashboard in a web browser for further configuration and pipeline management: <http://localhost:8080>.

- **Configure Access to FEAST Telemetry Data:**

- **Create Service Account and Role Binding for Data Access:** Creates a service account in the mlops namespace with permissions to access data in the monitoring namespace, where FEAST is deployed.

```
kubectl create serviceaccount feast-access -n mlops
kubectl create rolebinding feast-access-binding --
serviceaccount=mlops:feast-access --clusterrole=view -n
monitoring
```

- **Update Pipeline Scripts:** Ensure that your pipeline components include code to access FEAST data from the monitoring namespace. This involves configuring data sources and integrating them within the Kubeflow pipelines.

8.4 OpenNebula orchestrator deployment plan

The next step after training and evaluation is to retrieve the registered model for encapsulation and move to the production stage in the form of a model prediction service. The Orchestrator deployment consists of the following components:

Figure 5 Planned deployment of the orchestrator

- **Front-end:** The OpenNebula front-ends will be running on Ubuntu 22.04, providing the following services:
 - OpenNebula 6.8.3 management daemon
 - Scheduler
 - Sunstone Server
 - FireEdge Server
 - MariaDB database
 - OneFlow and OneGate

Users will be authenticated against the OpenNebula database, no external components would be used. Passwords are stored in a hashed format. OpenNebula configuration will be oriented to maximize the number of API requests per second.

- **Virtualisation hosts:** Single virtualization host, corresponding to the same bare metal server as the OpenNebula frontend. Based on the KVM hypervisor with Ubuntu 22.04:
 - Stock libvirt and qemu-kvm packages
 - OpenNebula kvm node package
 - User oneadmin to manage storage, networking and virtualization
 - Ruby package installed (used by monitoring probes and action scripts)

Hosts do not include any special PCI device. Capacity of the cloud can be scaled up either by adding more homogenous hosts to the existing cluster, or by creating a new cluster with additional and potentially different hosts.

- **Networking:** Virtualization host has a 10 Gbps NIC. I2CAT makes use of the following networks:
 - Public for front-end and guests' internet access. This network is sustained by the only 10Gbps NIC available and requires no VLAN encapsulation.
 - Private for inter VM private communication. This network is internal to the server and its traffic will not reach the networking infrastructure. Its main purpose is allowing the communication between Kubernetes nodes on the OneKE appliance. For the Private network it is possible to enforce Security Groups over VMs. Using Security Groups, administrators can define the firewall rules and apply them to the Virtual Machines, defining permitted INBOUND/OUTBOUND traffic.
- **Provisioning Model**
 - **Multi-tenancy:** The Cloud will have three different types of users:
 - Cloud Admins. Role reserved to the company IT staff. They will have admin privileges and will belong to the group "oneadmin".
 - Group Admins. They are allowed to manage virtual resources that belong to that Group, as well as new users. They are allowed to use physical resources associated with each of the VDCs the Group has access to, in a transparent way.
 - Customers or End users. Instantiate and manage Virtual Machines based on the predefined setups defined by both the Cloud and Group admins. Note that neither Group Admins nor End users can directly access or query the underlying infrastructure, such as storage mechanisms, locations other than the one granted access to or hosts. They will only manage virtual resources. An advanced provisioning model will be implemented that can be easily switched to a basic one.
 - **VDC Configuration:** The initial installation has one Demo VDCs that grants access to Cluster0, which in turn contains all the KVM hosts as well as all the virtual networks and datastores. This VDC configuration is intended only for test purposes and the Customer is encouraged to change it according to their own use.
 - **Appliances:** At the end of this installation a base Ubuntu2204 image will be added to the cloud with permissions to all the users so they can try all the options offered by the infrastructure. The images will be golden images that can be used to create new VMs or cloned to create new derived ones. The Cloud will be connected to the OpenNebula marketplace so admins can import images for other distributions. The OneKE appliance will be downloaded and launched based on the customer requirements.

9 Validation Timeline

AP	Description	Deadline	By
AP1	As a first step, collection of cloud-oriented metrics from Kubernetes (at OPTA premises), storage in influxDB and aggregation in FEAST	30/06/2024	OPTA
AP2	K8s clusters deployment by OPNEB (edge) and I2CAT (cloud)	31/07/2024	OPNEB-I2CAT
AP3	Deploy the orchestrator at edge	31/07/2024	OPNEB
AP4	Deploy i2CAT MLOps and OPTARE telemetry in dedicated namespaces at the cloud server	31/08/2024	I2CAT-OPTA
AP5	Deploy the holoportation app stack at the edge and collection of XR-oriented metrics by OPTARE telemetry system	31/08/2024	I2CAT-OPTA
AP6	Connect the i2CAT MLOps pipeline with FEAST offline data, train the NeSy model and serve it to the orchestrator	30/09/2024	I2CAT-OPTA
AP7	Orchestrator makes scaling decisions based on FEAST online data and NeSy pre-trained model	30/09/2024	OPNEB-OPTA
AP8	Test the intelligent scaling based on holoportation collected data and export validation metrics (defined in the previous deliverables) + analysis	31/10/2024	ALL

10 Conclusion

In conclusion, Deliverable E6.1 has detailed the validation plan within Task A6.1, including the deployment of key components such as the i2CAT Holoportation Stack, OPTARE monitoring platform, I2CAT MLOps Kubeflow pipeline, and OpenNebula orchestrator. At the time of writing, the testbed setup with "Higher End" and "Edge" servers has been completed, with Kubernetes clusters and namespaces organized for efficient deployment. The holoportation system deployment plan has been presented, including Holo Comm Server installation and client connections. The deliverable has also outlined KPIs and metrics management using Prometheus and OPTARE distributed telemetry system, with data stored in InfluxDB and features managed via FEAST. The i2CAT MLOps pipeline as well as OpenNebula orchestrator deployment steps have been detailed,, which includes front-end, virtualization, and networking components.